

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of 3-(3'-Carboxyphenylsulphonamido)-2- aryl-5H-4-thiazolidinone

S. N. JOSHI, K. D. SHAH, N. A. CHAUHAN
and
A. J. BAXI*

Department of Chemistry, Sauiashtra University,
Rajkot-360 005

Manuscript received 17 June 1991, revised 26 September 1991,
accepted 7 November 1991

THIAZOLIDINONES have been found to exhibit wide spectrum of pharmacological activities¹ and are nontoxic. A number of new 4-thiazolidinones were, therefore, prepared by conventional route and screened for antimicrobial activity. Thus, 3-(*N*-sulphonylhydrazino)benzoic acid², was condensed

Scheme 1

with different aromatic aldehydes to give the respective hydrazones (**1**) which were then condensed with thioglycolic acid to give the corresponding 4-thiazolidinones (**2**). The compounds were characterised by elemental analyses, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data. The compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal reference.

m-Carboxyphenylbenzalhydrazino sulphone (**1a**): A mixture of 3-(*N*-sulphonylhydrazino)benzoic acid² (0.216 g, 0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (1.06 g, 0.01 mol) in dioxane was refluxed for 3 h and then poured into crushed ice. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from methanol-dioxane (3 : 1) to give **1a**, (75%), m.p. 184° (Found: C, 55.25; H, 3.95; N, 9.0. C₁₄H₁₂N₂O₅S requires: C, 55.26; H, 3.94; N, 9.21%); ν_{max} 3 300 (N-H), 1 685 (C=O), 1 600 (-N=CH-Ar), 1 310 and 1 170 cm⁻¹ (S=O); δ 6.1 (1H, s, NH), 7.4-7.8 (5H, m, ArH), 7.9 (1H, s, N-CH), 8.88 (3H, m, ArH) and 10.0 (1H, s, COOH).

Similarly other hydrazones were prepared: **1b** (63%), 95°; **c** (75), 221°; **d** (60), 216°; **e** (92), 235°; **f** (84), 209°; **g** (81), 202°; **h** (80), 210°; **i** (84), 229°; **j** (50), 215°; **k** (48), 191°; **l** (71), 186°; **m** (22), 215°; **n** (65), 222°; **o** (64), 204°.

3-(3'-Carboxyphenylsulphonamido)-2-aryl-5H-4-thiazolidinone (**2a**): A mixture of *m*-carboxyphenylbenzalhydrazino sulphone (3.04 g, 0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid was condensed on an oil-bath at 120-130° for 6-8 h. The mixture was then cooled and washed with sodium bicarbonate to neutralise excess of thioglycolic acid. As the parent compound was also soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution, hence, the solution was neutralised with dilute HCl to isolate the 4-thiazolidinone which was crystallised from methanol-dioxane (4 : 1) to give **2a** (62%), m.p. 189-90° (Found: C, 49.58; H, 3.65; N, 7.1; S, 16.8. C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₅S₂ requires: C, 50.79; H, 3.70; N, 7.4; S, 16.93%); ν_{max} 3 200 (N-H), 1 680 (C=O), 1 370 and 1 170 (S=O), 1 280 (-C-N-C) and 756 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂-C), 5.4 (1H, s, NH), 7.2 (1H, s, N-CH), 7.3-7.7, 7.8-8.3 (each 4H, m, ArH) and 10.0 (1H, s, COOH).

Similarly other hydrazones were prepared: **2b** (40%), 105°; **c** (66), 222°; **d** (61), 217°; **e** (81), 210°; **f** (62), 212°; **g** (73), 170°; **h** (75), 195°; **i** (80) 212°; **j** (48), 188°; **k** (70), 194°; **l** (50), 52°; **m** (72), 204°; **n** (80), 215°; **o** (69), 182°.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening of compounds **1** and **2** was carried out using cup-plate method³ at a concentration of 50 μg using DMF as solvent against the bacteria *Staphylococcus*

citrus (2087), *S. aureus* (4150), *Escherichia coli* (2116) and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (2141) and the fungi *Candida albicans* (3100) and *Aspergillus flavus* (2210).

Most of the compounds were found moderately active against the different strains of bacteria and fungi but none was found to possess significant antimicrobial activity.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. A. R. Parikh, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University for facilities and to the Government of Gujarat for the award of a research scholarship to one of them (S.N.J.).

References

1. H. JENSH, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1937, **31**, 8123.
2. R. J. W. CREMLYN, *J. Chem. Soc., (C)*, 1968, 11.
3. A. L. BARRY, "The Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test Principle and Practices", 1979, pp. 180-193.